

MIRIZZI SYNDROME TYPE II WITH CHOLECYSTO-CHOLEDOCHAL FISTULA: A CASE REPORT

Sindromul Mirizzi tip II cu fistulă colecisto-coledociană: studiu de caz

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Summary. Mirizzi syndrome (MS) is a rare complication of longstanding gallstone disease, characterized by extrinsic compression or fistulization of the common bile duct (CBD) by an impacted calculus in the gallbladder infundibulum or cystic duct. Type II MS, defined by a cholecysto-choledochal fistula involving less than one-third of the CBD circumference, accounts for approximately 38% of MS cases in national surgical series, while preoperative diagnosis remains challenging and is often established only intraoperatively. We report the case of a 62-year-old male patient admitted to the Hepato-Biliary-Pancreatic Surgery Department of the IMSP Republican Clinical Hospital (RCH), Chișinău, Republic of Moldova, with a 10-day history of right hypochondrial pain, jaundice, nausea and vomiting. The workup included abdominal ultrasonography (USG), endoscopic retrograde cholangiopancreatography (ERCP), laboratory investigations and intraoperative findings. USG revealed a dilated CBD (33 mm), a thickened gallbladder wall (5–7.5 mm) and perivesicular col-

lections, whereas ERCP confirmed MS type II with a visible cholecysto-choledochal fistula, biliary stenting being performed successfully. Laboratory findings showed cholestasis, hepatocytolysis, reactive pancreatitis and electrolyte imbalances. Open cholecystectomy with repair of the 0.6 cm CBD defect on a Kehr T-tube drainage was performed, and histopathology confirmed chronic calculous cholecystitis with acute exacerbation, with an uneventful postoperative course. MS type II remains a surgical challenge that requires a multidisciplinary preoperative approach; the combination of ERCP with biliary stenting and open cholecystectomy with Kehr drainage proved safe and effective, with a favourable clinical outcome over 17 days of hospitalization. Accurate classification according to Csendes 2008 is essential for tailoring the surgical technique.

Key words: Mirizzi syndrome; cholecystocholedochal fistula; common bile duct; Kehr drainage; ERCP; cholelithiasis.

Introduction. Mirizzi syndrome (MS) is a rare but serious complication of chronic cholelithiasis, first described by Pablo Luis Mirizzi in 1948. It is defined by extrinsic compression of the common hepatic or common bile duct (CBD) by a calculus impacted in the gallbladder infundibulum or cystic duct, with or without a cholecysto-biliary fistula, and its overall incidence ranges from 0.7% to 1.4% among patients undergoing cholecystectomy¹.

The Csendes 2008 classification, the most widely adopted, defines five types based on the degree of CBD involvement: type I (extrinsic compression without fistula), type II (fistula occupying less than one-third of the CBD circumference), type III (one-third to two-thirds CBD involvement), type IV (more than two-thirds or complete CBD destruction), and type V (any type with an additional cholecysto-enteric fistula). Type II is the most frequently encountered form in national series, representing 38.3% of cases².

Preoperative diagnosis is notoriously difficult, being achieved in fewer than 30% of cases, as the clinical and radiological presentation mimics malignant biliary obstruction. The combination of abdominal ultrasonography (USG), endoscopic retrograde cholangiopancreatography (ERCP) and magnetic resonance cholangiopancreatography (MRCP) constitutes the recommended diagnostic algorithm³.

¹ Erben, Y.; Benavente-Chenhalls, L.A.; Donohue, J.M.; Que, F.G.; Kendrick, M.L.; Reid-Lombardo, K.M.; Farnell, M.B.; Nagorney, D.M. Diagnosis and treatment of Mirizzi syndrome: 23-year Mayo Clinic experience, in: *Journal of the American College of Surgeons*, 2011, vol. 213, nr. 1, pp. 114-119; Ferdohleb, A. Eficiența clinico-funcțională a tratamentului chirurgical al stricturilor biliare benigne. Teză de doctor habilitat, specialitatea Chirurgie. Chișinău, 2020. Disponibil online în Repozitoriul USMF, handle: 20.500.12710/31204; Ferdohleb, A. *Eficiența clinico-funcțională a tratamentului chirurgical contemporan al stricturilor biliare benigne*. Monografie. Chișinău: USMF „Nicolae Testemițanu”, 2018. 295 p. Disponibil online în Repozitoriul USMF, handle: 20.500.12710/30652.

² Tataria, R.D.; Salgaonkar, H.P.; Maheshwari, G.; Halder, P.J. Mirizzi syndrome: a scoring system for preoperative diagnosis, in: *Saudi Journal of Gastroenterology*, 2018, vol. 24, nr. 5, pp. 274-281; 3; Ji, X.; Yang, Z.; Ma, S.R.; Jia, W.; Zhao, Q.; Xu, L.; Kan, Y.; Cao, Y.; Wang, Y.; Fan, B.J. Use of different pathology classification systems in the preoperative imaging of Mirizzi syndrome, in: *Archives of Medical Science*, 2019, vol. 15, nr. 5, pp. 1288-1294; Kulkarni, S.S.; Hotta, M.; Sher, L.; Selby, R.R.; Parekh, D.; Buxbaum, J.; Stapfer, M. Complicated gallstone disease: diagnosis and management of Mirizzi syndrome, in: *Surgical Endoscopy*, 2017, vol. 31, nr. 5, pp. 2215-2222.

³ Moosa, H.; Jaffer, S.; Khan, M.N.; Aftab, A.; Hussain, R.; Mirza, A.; Zuberi, M.A.W.; Iftikhar, A.; Shah, H.H.; Patoli, S.; Jobran, A.W.M.; Yusuf, F.H.; Rauf, S.A. Mirizzi syndrome: clinical insights, diagnostic challenges and surgical outcomes. A 5-year experience in a tertiary care hospital in Pakistan, in: *Qatar Medical Journal*, 2025, vol. 2025, nr. 1, art. 8; Bueno Lledó, J.; Barber, S.M.;

Surgical management of MS type II consists of partial cholecystectomy and repair of the CBD defect, preferably with a Kehr T-tube drainage or hepaticojejunostomy depending on the extent of the fistula. We report a detailed case of MS type II diagnosed and treated at the IMSP Republican Clinical Hospital (RCH), Chișinău, Republic of Moldova, with a favourable surgical outcome⁴.

Case Presentation.

Patient demographics and presentation.

A 62-year-old male patient (B., born 05.06.1954, resident of the Republic of Moldova) was admitted on 17.02.2017 at 18:15 to the Hepato-Biliary-Pancreatic Surgery Department (Ward 3) of the IMSP Republican Clinical Hospital (RCH), Chișinău, Republic of Moldova. He was referred by the Emergency Medical Service, following a 10-day history (onset 07.02.2017) of progressive right hypochondrial and epigastric pain radiating to the right shoulder and lumbar belt, associated with nausea, vomiting and general weakness. Outpatient treatment had been administered without improvement⁵.

The patient denied alcohol consumption, tobacco use and known drug allergies. No significant hereditary or infectious disease history was recorded (HIV, HBV, HCV negative). A past history of tuberculosis contact was noted.

Physical examination. On admission, the patient was in a moderate general condition. Vital signs were as follows: blood pressure 125/85 mmHg, pulse 73 bpm, respiratory rate 18/min. The skin and mucous membranes were icteric/subicteric. Abdominal examination revealed tenderness on palpation in the right hypochondrium and epigastric region; the abdomen was soft and Murphy's sign was positive. No palpable lymphadenopathy was found, and Giordano's sign was negative bilaterally.

Ibáñez, J.C.; Torregrosa, A.G.; López-Andújar, R. Update on the diagnosis and treatment of Mirizzi syndrome in the laparoscopic era: our experience in 7 years, in: *Surgical Laparoscopy, Endoscopy & Percutaneous Techniques*, 2014, vol. 24, nr. 6, pp. 495-501; Lai, W.; Huang, Y.; Wei, W.; Zheng, H.; Yang, Y.; Zhou, Y. Effect of endoscopic retrograde cholangiopancreatography combined with laparoscopy and choledochoscopy on the treatment of Mirizzi syndrome, in: *Chinese Medical Sciences Journal*, 2013, vol. 28, nr. 2, pp. 72-77.

⁴ Ferdohleb, A.; Anton, M. Aspecte contemporane în diagnosticul și tratamentul sindromului Mirizzi, in: *Buletinul Academiei de Științe a Moldovei. Științe Medicale*, 2019, nr. 4(64), pp. 88-94; Cucu, I.; Ferdohleb, A. Managementul chirurgical în abordarea diferitelor tipuri de sindrom Mirizzi, in: *Patrimoniul cultural de ieri. Implicații în dezvoltarea societăților durabile de mâine*, ed. a XI-a, Chișinău, 11-12 februarie 2025, pp. 284-285; Cucu, I.; Ferdohleb, A.; Hotineanu, A. Sindromul Mirizzi: sinteză narativă, in: *Patrimoniul cultural de ieri. Implicații pentru dezvoltarea societății de mâine*, ed. a X-a, Chișinău, 19-20 septembrie 2024, pp. 593-599; Cucu, I.; Hotineanu, A.; Ferdohleb, A. Sindromul Mirizzi: particularități de diagnostic și opțiuni de tratament chirurgical, in: *Buletinul Academiei de Științe a Moldovei. Științe Medicale*, 2022, nr. 3(74), pp. 156-162; Hotineanu, A.; Cazacov, V.; Ferdohleb, A. ș.a. *Recomandări practice de diagnostic și tratament a pacientului chirurgical*. Chișinău: 2024.

⁵ Chen, Y.; Wu, S.; Wang, L.; Yang, J. Surgical strategies for Mirizzi syndrome: a ten-year single-center experience, in: *World Journal of Gastrointestinal Surgery*, 2022, vol. 14, nr. 2, pp. 107-119; Sui, X.; Li, M.; Zhang, D. Clinical outcomes and treatment strategy of Mirizzi's syndrome treated with surgery, in: *The American Surgeon*, 2025, vol. 91, nr. 1, pp. 31-37. DOI: 10.1177/00031348241267955; Brunt, L.M.; Deziel, D.J.; Telem, D.A.; Strasberg, S.M.; Agarwal, R.; Asbun, H. et al. Safe Cholecystectomy Multi-Society Practice Guideline and State-of-the-Art Consensus Conference on Prevention of Bile Duct Injury During Cholecystectomy, in: *Annals of Surgery*, 2020, vol. 272, nr. 1, pp. 3-23.

Diagnostic workup - laboratory investigations. The hemogram revealed leukocytosis ($11.0\text{--}12.0 \times 10^9/\text{l}$, subsequently $4.0 \times 10^9/\text{l}$ post-treatment), haemoglobin 128–132 g/l, haematocrit 0.34–0.39 and an elevated erythrocyte sedimentation rate (VSE 72 mm/h). The biochemical profile confirmed a cholestasis and hepatocytolysis syndrome: total bilirubin 22 $\mu\text{mol/l}$ (N: 3.3–18.8), direct bilirubin 8 $\mu\text{mol/l}$ (N: <3.3), AST 67 mmol/l/h (N: 0.1–0.45) and ALT 88 mmol/l/h (N: 0.1–0.68). Serum amylase was elevated at 62 g/l/h (N: 16–30), consistent with reactive pancreatitis. Significant electrolyte imbalances were documented: hyponatraemia (130 mmol/l; N: 135–145) and marked hypocalcaemia (calcium 2.15 mmol/l; N: 2.25–2.75 mmol/l). Coagulation studies showed fibrinogen 3.9 g/l and a prothrombin index within normal limits, while blood glucose fluctuated between 5.4 and 8.5 mmol/l.

Table 1. Key laboratory values at admission and during hospitalization

Parameter	Reference range	Admission	During hospitalization
Total bilirubin ($\mu\text{mol/l}$)	3.3–18.8	38 \uparrow	22 \uparrow
Direct bilirubin ($\mu\text{mol/l}$)	<3.3	22 \uparrow	8 \uparrow
AST (mmol/l/h)	0.1–0.45	70 \uparrow	67 \uparrow
ALT (mmol/l/h)	0.1–0.68	86 \uparrow	88 \uparrow
Amylase (g/l/h)	16–30	120 \uparrow	62 \uparrow
Calcium (mmol/l)	2.25–2.75	2.15 \downarrow	2.25
Sodium (mmol/l)	135–145	130 \downarrow	140
Leukocytes ($\times 10^9/\text{l}$)	4.0–9.0	14.0 \uparrow	11.0 \rightarrow 4.0
VSE (mm/h)	2–15	58 \uparrow	72 \uparrow
Haematocrit	0.36–0.48	0.39	0.34

Note: \uparrow = elevated above normal; \downarrow = below normal; N = normal range.

Ultrasonography (USG). Abdominal USG (exam no. 306, 17.02.2017, Republican Endoscopy Center, RCH) demonstrated hepatomegaly (right lobe 145 mm, left lobe 76 mm), a markedly dilated CBD measuring 33 mm (normal <8 mm), a deformed and thickened gallbladder wall (5–7.5 mm) with perivesicular fluid collections, and an enlarged pancreatic head (38 mm). These findings were strongly suggestive of extrahepatic biliary obstruction with associated reactive pancreatitis.

Endoscopic retrograde cholangiopancreatography (ERCP). ERCP was performed on 21.02.2017 and confirmed the diagnosis of MS type II, demonstrating a cholecysto-choledochal fistula involving less than one-third of the CBD circumference. A biliary stent was successfully placed to achieve biliary decompression and to facilitate preoperative optimization. The radiographic images (ARCADIS system) showed a clearly dilated CBD with the stent in situ.

Table 2. Preoperative diagnostic investigations

Investigation	Findings	Significance
USG abdomen (17.02.2017)	CBD 33 mm, gallbladder wall 5–7.5 mm, perivesicular fluid, pancreatic head 38 mm	Extrahepatic obstruction, reactive pancreatitis
ERCP (21.02.2017)	Cholecysto-choledochal fistula <1/3 CBD, stent placed	MS type II confirmed, biliary decompression
CT abdomen	Performed for differential diagnosis with malignancy	Excluded neoplasm

Investigation	Findings	Significance
Histopathology (U938)	Chronic calculous cholecystitis with acute exacerbation (hyperplastic)	Confirms underlying chronic inflammatory process

Surgical intervention. Following seven days of preoperative preparation, including biliary stenting, correction of electrolyte imbalances and general optimization, the patient underwent open surgical intervention on 24.02.2017 (protocol no. 133; start 11:30, end 13:15). Intraoperative findings confirmed MS type II: a cholecysto-choledochal fistula with a 0.6 cm CBD wall defect was identified. The procedure comprised an upper midline laparotomy, cholecystectomy with careful dissection of the inflammatory adhesions, identification and repair of the CBD fistula defect using primary closure, and Kehr T-tube biliary drainage of the CBD. Histopathological examination (no. U938, 02.03.2017) of the resected gallbladder specimen confirmed chronic calculous cholecystitis with acute hyperplastic exacerbation (four fragments; macroscopically, a fibrotic mucosa with adipose degeneration of the gallbladder wall and calculi).

Postoperative course and outcome. The patient was managed postoperatively in the Intensive Care Unit (TI no. 4) from 24.02.2017 to 27.02.2017 (three days), then transferred to the Hepato-Biliary-Pancreatic Surgery ward. A fistulography was performed postoperatively to verify biliary tract patency, and the postoperative period was uneventful. The patient was discharged on 06.03.2017 (17 days of total hospitalization) in an improved condition, with temporary work incapacity, and medical certificate no. 269844 was issued. Discharge recommendations included diet no. 5 (hepatobiliary), limitation of physical effort for 32 days, outpatient follow-up with the family physician, clinical control at one month and pharmacological treatment.

Discussion. MS type II is a surgically challenging entity that requires both accurate preoperative classification and individualized surgical planning. In this case, the clinical presentation – right hypochondrial pain, jaundice and elevated biliary enzymes in the context of a 10-day history – was consistent with published cohorts, in which MS typically presents with obstructive jaundice (52-100% of cases), pain (100%) and fever (61.6%). The USG finding of a CBD diameter of 33 mm was particularly striking. Although USG has a diagnostic sensitivity of only 8.3-27% for MS specifically, it provides essential preliminary data on biliary dilation and gallbladder morphology. In our case, the severely dilated CBD (>30 mm) directed attention toward a significant obstructive process, warranting ERCP.

ERCP, considered the gold standard for MS diagnosis with a mean sensitivity of 76.2%, confirmed the cholecysto-choledochal fistula and enabled simultaneous therapeutic biliary stenting, achieving CBD decompression before surgery. This two-stage approach – ERCP stenting followed by open surgery – is increasingly recommended for MS types II–III to reduce operative bleeding, improve visualization and allow optimization of comorbidities. Biochemically, the patient exhibited a complete cholestasis, hepatocytolysis–pancreatitis triad, with marked hypocalcaemia (2.15 mmol/l) that required specific correction. Hypocalcaemia in the context of acute pancreatitis and obstructive jaundice is a recognized marker of disease severity⁶.

⁶ Yuan, H.; Yuan, T.; Sun, X.; Zheng, M. A minimally invasive strategy for type II Mirizzi syndrome: combined endoscopic with laparoscopic approach, in: *Surgical Laparoscopy, Endoscopy & Percutaneous Techniques*, 2016, vol. 26, nr. 3, pp. 248-252; Senra, F.; Navaratne, L.; Acosta, A.;

The intraoperative CBD defect measured 0.6 cm ($<1/3$ CBD), confirming the Csendes type II classification. According to the national surgical series at RCH (73 patients, 2000–2022), type II accounted for 38.3% of MS cases, all managed with CBD defect repair on Kehr drainage – identical to the technique employed here. This approach preserves biliary continuity and avoids the complexity of hepaticojejunostomy, which is reserved for types III–IV. Limitations of this report include the absence of MRCP in the preoperative workup (which could have provided additional anatomical detail) and the retrospective nature of documentation from the medical records. Furthermore, long-term follow-up data beyond discharge are not available.

Conclusions. Mirizzi syndrome type II with a cholecysto-choledochal fistula is a rare but treatable complication of cholelithiasis. This case illustrates that accurate preoperative classification using ERCP - combined with biliary stenting, electrolyte correction and subsequent open cholecystectomy with Kehr T-tube drainage – yields excellent surgical outcomes. Intraoperative confirmation of the CBD defect size ($<1/3$ of the circumference) is essential for appropriate surgical technique selection according to the Csendes 2008 classification. Surgeons operating in high-volume biliary centres should maintain awareness of this entity in order to avoid iatrogenic CBD injury.

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